

Energy processes involved in CO adsorption on a modified Graphene-Based System

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Abstract

In this paper, the energy processes involved in CO adsorption on a graphene-based surface are investigated theoretically employing the density functional method. A theoretical model of carbon monoxide (CO) adsorption on a modified graphene sheet (one vacancy) was proposed. The analysis revealed that CO production favors an endothermic reaction, suggesting its potential use in a cooling system. These results provide a fundamental understanding of the thermodynamics of gas–graphene interactions and open possibilities for designing nanoscale refrigeration devices. Furthermore, the proposed model highlights the relevance of graphene-based materials as candidates for energy conversion and storage technologies, where adsorption-driven processes could be harnessed for innovative thermal management applications.

Key words: Density Functional Theory, carbon monoxide adsorption, cooling system

Introduction

The transportation sector represents one of the largest consumers of global energy, which consequently leads to considerable environmental consequences [1]. Therefore, it is crucial to establish strategies that harmonize environmental impacts with economic and social requirements [1]. Key concerns include waste generation such as discarded tires and oils, harmful emissions, and the intensification of global warming. To counter these issues, alternative fuels like hydrogen have been considered.

Within this framework, molecular hydrogen emerges as a carbon-free energy vector [2]. It is a renewable, clean, and non-toxic fuel, making it a strong candidate to substitute fossil fuels in vehicles [3], since its oxidation produces only water vapor and energy [4]. In addition, hydrogen's abundance and renewability make it a strategic energy source [5, 6], particularly because the electricity obtained from its oxidation has wide-ranging applications.

Nonetheless, the adoption of hydrogen as a fuel is still challenged by issues in production, transport, distribution, and storage. Regarding storage, solid-state technologies are still under development [4, 7–9]. Hydrogen storage plays a central role in the hydrogen economy, demanding solutions that are compact and lightweight [10]. Recent progress in volumetric and gravimetric energy density indicates that solid-state storage could deliver significant advantages for

automotive uses.

Compared with compressed gas or liquid storage methods—which require very high pressures (70 MPa) [3, 11] or cryogenic temperatures (20 K) [3, 12, 13]—solid-state storage is regarded as a safer and more practical option [3]. Although fossil fuels still surpass both compressed and liquid hydrogen in volumetric efficiency, lightweight solid materials could substantially improve the energy density of hydrogen tanks [10].

The efficiency of hydrogen storage materials is influenced by factors such as composition, structural properties, bonding, thermal stability, and other physical attributes [14]. Commonly investigated candidates include carbon-based materials, metal–organic frameworks (MOFs), zeolites, hydrides, and various intermetallic systems [15–26]. Their performance depends strongly on both intrinsic properties and external operating conditions.

Support structures, especially carbon-derived ones, are also crucial in enhancing reactivity and efficiency. Activated carbon is the most frequently employed, followed by carbon black [27]. Although other graphene-based surfaces have also proven useful for adsorbing molecules such as CO, CO₂, or N₂ [28, 29]. It would also be important to investigate different structures and mechanisms involving oxiborate [30–34] or trititanium pentoxide [35, 36] systems, or even magnetic interactions such as the formation of spin polarons [31, 37–47] and their interaction with dissociated

hydrogen as a significant contributor to hydrogen adsorption.

Solid-state hydrogen storage operates through adsorption and desorption mechanisms, in which hydrogen dissociation and activation are essential. Spillover effects may also boost storage capabilities [48]. In certain cases, molecular hydrogen dissociates on surfaces to create dihydride complexes, with the nature of the substrate influencing these processes.

The paper is structured as follows: the Methodology section presents the computational approaches, including the theoretical models, simulation parameters, and numerical procedures employed to ensure the accuracy and reproducibility of the study. The Results and Discussion section provides a detailed account of the findings, highlighting both qualitative and quantitative aspects. In particular, it examines the energetic properties obtained from the simulations. Finally, the Conclusions section summarizes the main contributions of the work, emphasizing the novelty of the findings and outlining possible directions for future research.

1. Methodology

Computational simulations were carried out using the Quantum Espresso package [49, 50], the projector-augmented wave (PAW) method [51] was employed to perform Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations, which has become a standard tool for modeling problems in physics, chemistry, materials science, and various branches of engineering [52]. Understanding and controlling matter at the atomic and molecular levels is essential for advancing high-level engineering, including refrigeration technology, since thermal phenomena arise from atomic-scale energetic processes. For the exchange-correlation energy, the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) [53] functional was used. The valence electron configurations considered were ($2s^2 2p^2$) for carbon and ($2s^2 2p^4$) for oxygen. All calculations used a plane-wave cutoff energy of 500 eV and a $12 \times 12 \times 1$ k-point mesh, ensuring energy convergence within 0.001 eV/atom [7, 28, 29]. A force convergence criterion of 0.02 eV/Å was applied. The theoretical model employed a slab of (5x5) hexagonal periodic unit cell with one vacancy see Figure 1 and one CO molecule. The z-axis dimension of 15.8753 Å was chosen to minimize interlayer interactions under periodic boundary conditions. In the same way, the nudged elastic band method [54] was used to locate transition states. The former methodology was employed to investigate the reaction mechanisms involved in CO adsorption on the defective graphene-based surface. Finally, visualization of theoretical structures was performed using the Xcrysden software [55].

Fig. 1. Modified graphene (MG) system (49 carbon atoms and one vacancy) The yellow circles represent the carbon atoms, the yellow lines represent the bonds between the carbon atoms.

2. Results and Discussion

Two minima and one transition state were identified in this work using the nudged elastic band method [54]. The minima were confirmed by vibrational analysis showing only positive (or negligible) frequencies, while the transition state exhibited a single imaginary frequency.

In Figure 1, the modified graphene (MG) structure consisting of 49 carbon atoms and a single vacancy is shown. A carbon monoxide (CO) molecule was added to this structure, and the system was subsequently optimized, yielding a stable configuration with a distance of 3.4367 Å between the CO molecule and the graphene surface. This distance is defined between the carbon atom of the CO molecule and the nearest carbon atom of the modified graphene surface, as illustrated more clearly in Figure 2.

The intramolecular distance between carbon and oxygen in CO is 1.1443 Å, which is slightly larger (by approximately 1%) than the experimental value of 1.1280 Å. This deviation arises from the interaction between the modified graphene surface and the CO molecule. It is also worth noting that the interlayer spacing of modified graphene along the z-axis (vertical direction) is 15.8753 Å. This value was chosen to model a single layer of modified graphene, thereby avoiding interlayer interactions and the formation of a three-dimensional system.

Additionally, this system exhibits a slight paramagnetic behavior of $0.2460 \mu_B$, localized around the carbon atoms neighboring the vacancy. It should be emphasized that pristine graphene is not paramagnetic but diamagnetic. This is because graphene has a closed-shell configuration (all electron spins are paired within each energy level), and the diamagnetic response arises mainly from electron circulation in the π orbitals.

Fig. 2. A side view of the modified graphene system with a CO molecule at a distance of 3.4367 Å is shown. The yellow circles represent the carbon atoms, the yellow lines represent the bonds between the carbon atoms. Red circle is the oxygen atom. The side view of the surface is shown to better visualize the interaction with the CO molecule.

Figure 3 shows the modified graphene system interacting with a carbon monoxide (CO) molecule. A clear chemical interaction is observed, leading to the adsorption of the CO molecule onto the modified graphene surface. In this context, the system can be described as oxidized modified graphene (GMO). The carbon-carbon distance is now 3.3316 Å, which can be compared to the previous model value of 3.4367 Å. Likewise, the carbon-oxygen bond length of the CO molecule increases to 1.1692 Å, significantly larger than the 1.1443 Å observed in the earlier system.

The simulations also indicate that this system does not exhibit magnetism, either in terms of paramagnetism ($0.0 \mu_B$) or due to unpaired electrons. Compared with the previous system, this suggests the possibility of a magnetic transition in CO adsorption systems, with further details to be presented in a forthcoming article, in the same way, the total characterization of the transition state involved will be left for a future article.

The adsorption process of CO(g) is exothermic, releasing approximately 159.2 kJ/mol of energy. The reverse reaction, leading to the production of CO(g), is endothermic, which suggests that this system could be considered as a potential component in a refrigeration cycle. In this way, the unique properties of graphene and graphene oxide could be exploited for applications in the refrigeration industry.

3. Conclusions

The theoretical model presented in this study, based on a modified graphene system of one vacancy, demonstrates the potential to act both as a CO adsorption medium and as a

Fig. 3. This figure shows the interaction of the modified graphene surface and the carbon monoxide molecule. With reference to Figure 2.

CO production system. The adsorption of CO(g) onto the modified graphene surface is an exothermic process, releasing approximately 159.2 kJ/mol of energy. Conversely, the reverse reaction, which leads to the generation of CO(g), is endothermic, indicating that the system could be utilized in reversible processes. This dual functionality suggests that the modified graphene system could be integrated as a functional component within a refrigeration cycle, taking advantage of the heat exchange associated with CO adsorption and desorption. Furthermore, these findings highlight the broader potential of graphene and graphene oxide, whose exceptional chemical and thermal properties can be leveraged to develop innovative solutions for energy-efficient cooling and refrigeration technologies.

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